

PROGRESS IN DEVELOPING SiC/SiC COMPOSITE MATERIALS FOR ADVANCED NUCLEAR REACTORS

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Abstract - SiC_f/SiC composite is a refractory material which presents an excellent mechanical behavior in very harsh conditions (high temperature and high irradiation flux). Initially conceived as cladding materials for the Fourth generation Gas cooled Fast Reactor (GFR), this material has been recently envisaged by CEA for different core structures of Sodium Fast Reactor (SFR) which combines fast neutrons and high temperature (700°C). We describe herein the last improvements regarding fabrication of tubular SiC_f/SiC composites through CVI route for generic in-core structures applications.

1 Introduction

Regarding their physical and chemical properties as well as their stability under irradiation and safety features, SiC_f/SiC composites are of prime interest for nuclear applications in fusion or advanced fission reactors.

Past efforts to apply these materials for fuel cladding have highlighted different technological barriers, the main ones concerning both the lack of impermeability to fission gases and the suggested designs of concept that were not consistent with the ceramic composite manufacturing. For this reason, the French Alternative Energies and Atomic Energy Commission (CEA) has recently reoriented its research activities on a “pin cladding concept” which seems to be more adapted to meet the specifications [1-2]. The recent advancements in braiding and filament winding techniques make these technologies very attractive for SiC_f/SiC manufacturers. Combined to a densification by the chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) process, new tubular composite structures with rather high

mechanical properties and close to geometric tolerances have been elaborated.

This paper outlines the last significant results obtained for development of new tubular SiC_f/SiC composite structures.

2 The SiC_f/SiC pin cladding concepts

Looking ahead to demonstrating the feasibility of manufacturing a pin fuel cladding in SiC_f/SiC composite, two tubular concepts were suggested : the cladding concept of “all-ceramic” which forms as a reference as opposed to the “ceramic/metal” concept resorting to the use of a metal liner.

Regarding works conducted in ref.[3], the main idea in this current research was to develop a mechanically robust ceramic tubular clad structure that is impermeable to fission gases at normal and abnormal reactor operating conditions. The approach followed was to combine the advantageous properties of the different technologies shaping of fiber reinforcement to form a hybrid ceramic composite material with high density and good damage tolerance. Also, beyond the elastic limit of multi-layered composites marked by the appearance of matrix cracking, leading to leakage, the presence of compatible metal liner was added to ensure impermeability.

3 Fabrication of optimized weaving

An ambitious program of manufacturing of fibrous composite materials was thus undertaken in order to obtain a final object with the right geometry: typically, length: ~2m, outer diameter: 10mm and thickness: 1mm. In a first step, fabrication focused on a 20 centimeters long tube which is enough to evaluate R&D solutions.

So, for the tubular geometry, the technique of the braiding was studied at first. Actually, 2D braids with angles of 45° and 60° were prepared then densified by chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) at CEA.

However, if 2D braiding presents a real interest from the mechanical behavior point of view, 3D braiding (interlock type) seems - a priori - preferable because of the expected gap in thermal conductivity (through the thickness of the tube) and in resistance to interlaminar shear. For this purpose, 3D weaves were also prepared then densified in the same way. The important feature is that these 3D braids have been realized for the first time to our knowledge from high purity silicon carbide fibers (Hi-Nicalon S or Tyranno SA3, cf. fig.1).

2D braiding pin specimen (3 layers 45°) thickness ~ 0.9 mm *3D braiding pin specimen thickness ~ 0.8 mm*

Fig.1. 2D and 3D braiding pins.

Besides, it is important to point out that strict respect of both the dimensions and the high geometric tolerance for the pin cladding is a major criteria, imposed by the designers. Thus, in order to ensure an acceptable roughness of the inner surface while keeping high mechanical properties, investigations on filament winding process have been performed.

Very favorable results have been recently obtained as illustrated in fig. 2. No machining was necessary to get the very smooth inner surface.

Fig.2. Transverse section of a tube obtained by filament winding without post-machining.

It should be noted here that SiC densification of fibrous preforms by CVI shows a distribution of different porosity depending on the nature of the reinforcement. High densities (greater than 2.50) can be obtained for wound and 2D braided composites, while 3D braiding only leads to modest densities of about 2.10 (porosity corresponding of ~ 30% which is advisable to fill in to keep a high thermal conductivity value).

4 Smoothing of the outer surface

To ensure compliance with external dimensions and tolerances, use of a ceramic coating smoothing is studied, as well as the use of machining by “centerless grinding” whose effect on the overall mechanical behavior remains to be validated.

As for the first route, spin coating technique was proposed and investigated on plate geometry. Significant work has been done to optimize the formulation of suspensions and process parameters (speed, number of deposits, etc.). Initially, the suspensions were prepared from submicron-SiC powders α commercial and a specific precursor polymer AHPC. In the future, the use of nanosized β -SiC powders is preferred.

SiC coatings were thermally treated in a cycle optimized at LCTS and leading to the conversion of the precursor system. Finally, the SiC coatings have been characterized (XRD, microprobe analysis, SEM observation, density measurement and optical profilometry).

As shown in Figure 3, good results were obtained, since the average roughness (Ra) of the initial composite was significantly reduced from a Ra ~ 59 μm to 22 μm . More details on process and optimal parameters are given in reference [4].

Fig.3. 2D and 3D profilometries of the surface of a SiC_f/SiC composite with and without coating.

5 Mechanical properties

A series of mechanical tests will then be carried out under axial tensile load to evaluate the mechanical behavior for the different types of materials. To do this, an extension system for performing tests on tubes has especially been developed. As an example, a comparison of the test results for different 2D and 3D interlock braiding structures with or without filament winding was reported in fig. 4. The characteristic dimensions of the tubes are between 8 mm and 10 mm, respectively for the inner and outer diameters and length equal to 60 mm.

From these curves, it can be assumed that CEA materials have high level mechanical properties. The importance of the fibrous architecture on mechanical properties is also demonstrated.

Fig.4. Stress-strain curves obtained in tensile load for different types of composite structures.

As expected, a better behavior under pure tensile loading is obtained for 2D braided tubes at 45 ° in comparison to those with an angle of 60 °. The bundling of filament winding technology and 2D braiding improves mechanical properties. In particular, the proportional limit stress (PLS) is greatly increased. If our interest is the stress to failure, the best result is obtained for the 3D braided pin (about 450 MPa).

This study is under way and should lead to a lot of data to retain the most interesting architecture for the application. The evaluation of the effect of machining the outer surface of the tubes on the mechanical properties is also expected.

6 Conclusion

This paper was intended to assess achievements of materials testing in order to define the different components of the cladding.

The CVI process has shown the extent of its possibilities for the development of tubes through judicious selection of fiber architectures. Compliance with the geometric tolerance on the diameter of the tube can be achieved without machining operation for the inner surface; in addition, also performed on the majority of tubes, the strain to failure exceeds the target value of 0.5%. The work of smoothing the outer surface of the first

CMC gives satisfactory results; the method proves to be industrially reliable.

Future prospects are now expected to demonstrate the tightness of the pin cladding concept with and without the use of a metal liner.

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